

The Satisfaction of Souls and Words of the Wise concerning the scholars and righteous ones buried in Fez, by Muhammad ibn Ja'far al-Kattani

also known as “Kitab Salwat al-Anfas wa muhadathat al-akyas bi man uqbira min al-'ulama' wal-sulaha' bi Fas”

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Entry tags: Sufi, Religious Group, Arabic, Text, Hagiography, Language, Scholastic text, Religious History, North African Religion, Islamic Traditions

Biographical dictionary of religious scholars and Sufi saints buried in Fez, Morocco, arranged geographically according to burial site

Date Range: 1000 CE - 1898 CE

Region: Morocco

Region tags: Northern Africa, Africa, Morocco

Morocco

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Al-Kattani, Muhammad Ibn Ja'far. *Salwat al-Anfas wa Muhadathat al-Akyas bi man Uqbira min al-'Ulama' wa Sulaha' bi Fas* (Publisher Unknown; Lithograph, 1898)
- Source 2: Al-Kattani, Muhammad Ibn Ja'far. *Salwat al-Anfas wa Muhadathat al-Akyas bi man Uqbira min al-'Ulama' wa Sulaha' bi Fas* (Casablanca: Dar al-Thaqafah, 2004)
- Source 3: Al-Kattani, Muhammad Ibn Ja'far. *Salwat al-Anfas wa Muhadathat al-Akyas bi man Uqbira min al-'Ulama' wa Sulaha' bi Fas* (Rabat: Dar al-Aman, 2014; first edition 2004)

Notes: The lithograph print is purportedly the original, published in either 1898 or 1899. Although the publisher is unknown it could have been published by members of the al-Kattani family, who were involved in the nascent print industry in Morocco at the time. Worldcat lists several printings of this edition available at American libraries and one at Oxford. A digital scan of the second volume is publicly accessible through HathiTrust (see online sources). Out of the secondary sources, Amster, Bazzaz, and Dinnerlein all appear to rely primarily on this version. Landorf cites both the lithograph and the Rabat print edition. The Casablanca version (all 3 vols. also available online) is the version I have relied on and which Haitami appears to rely on. I am not familiar with any substantive differences between the various

versions, however, Bazzaz (below, note 6) notes that the editors of the print editions "have introduced a number of modern elements such as paragraphs, diacritical marks, separation of biographical entries from one another, and inclusion of the dates of death of each mutarjam at the beginning of the entry."

Reference: Bazzaz, Sahar. "Reading Reform Beyond the State: Salwat Al-anfas, Islamic Revival and Moroccan National History". *Journal of North African Studies* 13, no. 1 (March 2008): 1-13.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13629380701528853>.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=njp.32101020269328&seq=1>
- Source 1 Description: Second volume of the lithograph version of Salwat al-Anfas (see "Source 1" above)
- Source 2 URL: <https://archive.org/details/slwt-anfs-1/slwt-anfs-1/page/n1/mode/2up>
- Source 2 Description: All three volumes of the edited Casablanca version (see "Source 2" above)

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Impressed

Tool for making the impression(s)

- Other [specify]: Lithograph print

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Paper

Specify type of paper

- Specify: Modern parchment

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

- Other [specify]: N/A

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

- Other [specify]: Likely handwritten and edited by the author before printing

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Notes: There are a number of copies of the original lithograph print (from either 1898 or 1899) located at various libraries, including several in the U.S. and one at Oxford

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership: Elite Religious Specialists Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– I don't know

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– I don't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: The text is was considered subversive from the perspective of official Moroccan political authority, but was very popular in its day

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

- ↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?
 - No
- ↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?
 - No
- ↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?
 - No
- ↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?
 - No
 - ↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?
 - No
 - ↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?
 - No
- ↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?
 - No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

Notes: The Salwa has been described as both a biographical compendium of Moroccan saints and a guide to tomb visitation. As such, it is not a "ritual text" per se, but might be useful for the lesser ritual practice of saintly tomb visitation.

Reference: Landorf, Brittany. "Gendering Madness: Figuring the Majdhuba in Modern Moroccan Hagiography". *Body and Religion* 6, no. 1 (2022): 47-73. <https://doi.org/10.1558/bar.23222>.

↳ Is it orally recited?

– No

↳ Is it read?

– No

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: Visitation of tombs of Sufi saints

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– No

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– I don't know

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Specify: Saintly tomb visitation may happen at any time but is particularly popular on their birthdays, or may draw large crowds during celebrations of the birthday of the Prophet Muhammad

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– I don't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– I don't know

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– I don't know

Is there material significance to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Rather than arranging the biographies chronologically or alphabetically, al-Kattani arranges them geographically according to where the subjects are buried in Fez, beginning with the shrine of Mulay Idriss II, the founder of the city and purported first ruler of Morocco, and spiraling outward from there. The lithograph version is also materially significant for scholars, as it is an early example of a lithograph print related to Sufi practice, and in general central to Morocco's adoption of print technology (which came a bit later than other Arabic-speaking societies).

↳ Is it visible?

– Yes

↳ Is it hidden?

– No

↳ Can it be touched?

– Yes

↳ Does touching the text during ritual have a specific function?

– Yes

Notes: Touching the text does not have ritual efficacy, but since the biographies are arranged geographically, multiple scholars have suggested that al-Kattani may have intended the text to "function" as guide to tomb visitation. This is supported by the fact that the introduction, as Dinnerlein puts it, "reads like a veritable treatise on adab al-ziyara," that is, the ethics of saintly tomb visitation.

Reference: Dinnerlein, Bettina. "Asserting Religious Authority in Late 19th/early 20th Century Morocco Muhammad B. Ja'far Al-kattani (d. 1927) and His Kitab Salwat Al-anfas". In *Speaking for Islam: Religious Authorities in Muslim Societies*, edited by Gudrun Krämer and Sabine Schmidtke, 128–52. Leiden: Brill, 2006.

↳ Does the material significance have an esoteric function?

– I don't know

Notes: It's hard to say whether the text was intended to have any esoteric function from a ritual perspective. However, given the arrangement of biographies, scholars (especially Amster) have

suggested the text embodies a sort of "sacred geography" for the city of Fez and its scholar-saints.

Reference: Amster, Ellen. *Medicine and the Saints: Science, Islam, and the Colonial Encounter in Morocco, 1877-1956*. Austin: University of Texas Press, 2013.

↳ Does the text serve a protective function?
– No

↳ Does the text serve a healing function?
– I don't know

↳ Does the text serve a cleansing function?
– I don't know

↳ Does the text serve as a form of expiation?
– No

↳ Does the text serve as an incantation?
– No

↳ Has the materiality of the text been altered?
– Yes

Reference: Bazzaz, Sahar. "Reading Reform Beyond the State: Salwat Al-anfas, Islamic Revival and Moroccan National History". *Journal of North African Studies* 13, no. 1 (March 2008): 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13629380701528853>.

↳ Specify
– Specify: Critically edited and printed

Notes: Sahar Bazzaz notes that the editors of the modern, print edition "have introduced a number of modern elements such as paragraphs, diacritical marks, separation of biographical entries from one another, and inclusion of the dates of death of each mutarjam at the beginning of the entry" (Bazzaz 2008, note 6).

↳ Are there debates about whether or not altering the materiality of the text is acceptable?
– No

↳ Other important aspects of materiality with regard to the text?

– I don't know

Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?

Please specify the substances in the sub-questions

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Behavioral literature?

– No

Other

–Other [specify]: Biographical tradition

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

–Other [specify]: Biographical compendium

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Other [specify]: Maintenance of Sufi/saintly lineages often involves the passing of spiritual power or authority (often referred to as baraka) from leader to one of his followers. In this case, lineage is maintained through student-teacher relationships, but many of the other elements above may also obtain.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Yes

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– I don't know

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– Yes

Notes: Much Sufi discourse (in which the author al-Kattani would have been conversant) makes a distinction between a higher spirit/soul (the ruh) and lower, baser "self" (al-nafs), which do not necessarily equate with body/soul or spirit/mind binaries in Western (Christian or Enlightenment) thought. The distinction between ruh and nafs is moreover sometimes related to distinctions between an "inner" realm of spirit/experience (al-batin) and an external realm of appearances (al-zahir), though the relationship between the two binaries is not necessarily homologous.

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– I don't know

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Yes

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– I don't know

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– I don't know

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?

– Yes

↳ In cemetery?

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– I don't know

↳ Other formal burial type?

– Yes

Notes: Sainly tombs may occasionally be attached to a Sufi lodge (zawiya), a place for the practice of Sufi rituals where adherents may occasionally live or stay for extended time.

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: N/A

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– No

Notes: "Worship" cannot extend to any other beings besides God, even to the Sufi saints who, though possessing spiritual power and the ability to intercede, are not strictly speaking "divine"

↳ For the worship of a deified human?
– No

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?
– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?
– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?
– I don't know

Notes: Whether or not Sufi saints are "deified" is likely a problem of translation. They are ascribed spiritual power and the ability to perform miracles and intercede between humans and God, but they are not considered "deities" in the sense that God is.

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?
– Yes

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present
– I don't know

Notes: God is "present" in a way but primarily through the actions/intercession of the scholars and saints as mentioned by the author

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

Notes: The Sufi saints eulogized in al-Kattani's biographical compendium are thought to maintain their spiritual power (baraka) after death, along with the ability to respond to living human appeals and an ability to "intercede" on their behalf (though God remains the ultimate cause of human affairs)

↳ Human spirits can be seen
– Yes

Notes: The "human spirits" here would be the Sufi saints whose biographies the author includes

and whose tombs he maps out.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– Yes

Notes: Particularly when living humans may appeal to a saint's baraka for its healing abilities

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– I don't know

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– I don't know

- ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Specify: Can respond to pleas from living humans
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life
 - I don't know
 - ↳ In dreams
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination practices
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists
 - No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Communicate through other means

–Specify: Those seeking help from saints are known to make petitions in paper form

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Paranormal?

Notes: Likely jinn, spirits who at times inhabit the bodies of lay people and spiritual adepts, particularly those saints deemed "mad" (madhjub)

Reference: Landorf, Brittany. "Gendering Madness: Figuring the Majdhuba in Modern Moroccan Hagiography". *Body and Religion* 6, no. 1 (2022): 47-73. <https://doi.org/10.1558/bar.23222>.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Although this is mostly implied rather than explicit throughout the text, scholars and saints are often lauded for practices (most of them listed below) that are explicitly identified as "pleasing to God."

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– Yes

↳ Food

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s)

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– Yes

↳ Adultery

– Yes

↳ Incest

– Yes

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].

– No

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)

– No

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?

– No

↳ Other sexual practices

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other
 - Specify: General steadfastness of faith

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?
 - Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god
 - Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

Notes: Although this is more background to al-Kattani's text, effects of God in the world are sometimes rationalized by theologians as unfolding in accordance with certain universal, "natural" laws

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Notes: The implication of this-worldly reward is tied mainly to the idea that saintly figures mentioned in the text (both living and dead) are able to aid others by "interceding" on their behalf in their pleas to God

↳ Highly emphasized?

– Yes

↳ Consists of good luck?

– Yes

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– Yes

- ↳ Consists of success in battle?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of peace or social stability?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of success on journeys?
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?
 - Yes
- ↳ Other?
 - Specify: Financial prosperity, educational success

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– I don't know

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Notes: The Islamic tradition in general has its own eschatological discourse but it is not a matter of discussion in the *Salwat al-Anfas* itself

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Present (but not emphasized)

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts

– Yes

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities

– No

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)

– No

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical

– No

- ↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)
 - All individuals within society (Excepting slaves, aliens)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity
 - Yes

- ↳ Courage (in battle)
 - I don't know

- ↳ Courage (generic)
 - Yes

- ↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
 - Yes

- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
 - Yes

- ↳ Generosity/charity
 - Yes

- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
 - Yes

- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - Yes

- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - Yes

- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

Notes: Not so much mentioned as familial/filial piety as such, but often implied through the virtue of *suhba* noted below. However, al-Kattani likens the obedience of some Sufi women to their husbands to the obedience of a student to his master (see below).

Reference: El Haitami, Meriem. "Women and Sufism: Expression and the Political Sphere in Contemporary Morocco". *Mediterranean Studies* 2, no. 2 (2014): 190-212.

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

Notes: Usually glossed by the virtue of closeness (*suhba*) with one's spiritual/religious teacher, for example frequent statements about students who "remained close to" their teacher (*sahahab 'anhu*).

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– Yes

Notes: Though "creativity" and "freedom" are not Islamic virtues to the extent they are in European Enlightenment epistemologies, some of the Sufis (especially women) that al-Kattani mentions are included as "mad" saints (*majdhub*, m; *majdhuba*, f), that is for the way their bucking of traditional social mores gave them a certain spiritual charisma.

Reference: El Haitami, Meriem. "Women and Sufism: Expression and the Political Sphere in Contemporary Morocco". *Mediterranean Studies* 2, no. 2 (2014): 190-212.

Reference: Landorf, Brittany. "Gendering Madness: Figuring the *Majdhuba* in Modern Moroccan Hagiography". *Body and Religion* 6, no. 1 (2022): 47-73. <https://doi.org/10.1558/bar.23222>.

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– I don't know

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

Notes: Many figures are included in the biographical compendium as shurafa' (sing. sharif), that is, on account of their lineage traceable to the Prophet Muhammad

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

Notes: Although, as mentioned above, being "mad" (majdhub/a, i.e. the opposite of serene) could also help one accrue spiritual authority

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Yes

Notes: Joyfulness or enthusiasm is typically mentioned as a disposition toward the remembrance of God (dhikr)

↳ Optimism/hope

– I don't know

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

Notes: Wisdom/understanding, along with discernment/intelligence (below), are likely the most important virtues mentioned or implied in the text. In fact, Bettina Dinnerlein argues that although al-Kattani places scholars and saintly figures on equal planes of authority, there is an

implicit schematization whereby rationalist knowledge acquired through textual scholarship ('ilm) unlocks the potential for other types of spiritual insight (like ma'rifa), even if the latter is the ultimate goal of religious study and practice.

Reference: Dinnerlein, Bettina. "Asserting Religious Authority in Late 19th/early 20th Century Morocco Muhammad B. Ja'far Al-kattani (d. 1927) and His Kitab Salwat Al-anfas". In *Speaking for Islam: Religious Authorities in Muslim Societies*, edited by Gudrun Krämer and Sabine Schmidtke, 128–52. Leiden: Brill, 2006.

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

Notes: In a more aesthetic, rather than physical/bodily sense. A few of al-Kattani's entries for scholars known for Qur'an recitation, for example, describe them as "having a beautiful voice" (jamil al-sawt). By contrast, some of the (especially female) "mad" (majdhuba) saints are described as being disheveled.

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

Notes: Cleanliness as an outward manifestation of inner virtue, but see above note about the disheveled look of "mad" (majdhub) saints playing into their aura of (non-rational) spiritual insight

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: Some scholars are noted for their verbal eloquence. Sometimes the respectability of one's lineage is made into a virtue, particularly in the case of those descended from the Prophet (al-shurafa', sing. sharif)

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Notes: Fasting is, to my knowledge, not explicitly mentioned in the text but fasting during Ramadan is of course a central tenet of Islam generally. That background is instead more or less assumed for the author and readers.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Notes: Certain food taboos (like not consuming pork) are not necessarily mentioned but still part of the assumed background of author and readers as Muslims, generally.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 3

Notes: Those mentioned in the text are lauded for adherence to obligatory prayer (salat) as well as supererogatory rituals like the remembrance of God through vocal chanting (dhikr)

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– I don't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification?

– No

↳ Circumcision?

– I don't know

Notes: Circumcision is required according to Islamic law but to my knowledge is not explicitly mentioned in the text

↳ Food taboos?

– I don't know

↳ Hair?

– Yes

↳ Dress?

– Yes

Notes: Normative hair and dress are implied throughout, but norms are also asserted through the case of "mad" saints, whose "disheveled" look or rejection of normative dress are mentioned explicitly.

Reference: Landorf, Brittany. "Gendering Madness: Figuring the Majdhuba in Modern Moroccan Hagiography". *Body and Religion* 6, no. 1 (2022): 47-73. <https://doi.org/10.1558/bar.23222>.

↳ Ornaments?
– I don't know

↳ Archaic ritual language?
– Yes

↳ Other?
– Specify: N/A

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is universal?
– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is widespread?
– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon?
– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– I don't know

Notes: This may depend on what is considered "entertaining." The text certainly includes, for example, descriptions of miracles (karamat) performed by some of the scholars/saints who are included in the biographical compendium, but the purpose is primarily to testify to their authority through demonstration of spiritual power (baraka).

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A Faith Elect

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A Faith Elect

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: N/A

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– I don't know

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– I don't know

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– Yes

Notes: The text is not exactly proscriptive on this, but legitimizes a model of education predicated on direct, face-to-face and one-to-one relationships between teacher and student, undermined by an ethic/virtue of "closeness" with one's teacher (suhba, mentioned in another answer comment)

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– I don't know

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– I don't know

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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